

Appendix 7. Consent

Who is doing the research?

This survey is part of a research study conducted by researchers in at Dartmouth Medical School and the Department of Public Health in Norway who is also funding the study.

What is the goal of the research?

This study is being done to help us develop ways to communicate the results of medical research to members of the public. The information you will see summarizes a recent research trial done to test the effect of wearing glasses on your chance of getting COVID.

What will we ask you to do?

We will show you some information and ask you some questions to learn if the materials are clear. We will also ask a few questions about you (like your age). The whole survey will be conducted online.

It typically takes people about 20 minutes to complete the survey.

Who can participate?

Participation in this study is limited to individuals age-18 and older, who live in the US, and speak and read English.

Risks

The risks and discomfort associated with participation in this study are no greater than those ordinarily encountered in daily life or during other online activities.

Benefits

There may be no personal benefit from your participation in the study, but the knowledge received may be of value to humanity.

Costs

There will be no cost to you if you participate in this study.

Future Use of Information

In the future, once we have removed all identifiable information from your data (information), we may use the data for our future research studies, or we may distribute the data to other researchers for their research studies. We would do this without getting

additional informed consent from you. Sharing of data with other researchers will only be done in such a manner that you will not be identified.

Confidentiality

The collected data will be anonymous, and it will not be possible to trace back to the participants. Your IP address will not be captured.

Right to Ask Questions & Contact Information

If you have any questions about this study, you should feel free to ask them by contacting the co-principal investigator, Steven Woloshin (steven.woloshin@dartmouth.edu). If you have questions later, desire additional information, or wish to withdraw your participation, please use this email address as well.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is voluntary. You may discontinue participation at any time during the research activity. You may print a copy of this consent form for your records.

I am age 18 or older. Yes No

I have read and understand the information above. Yes No

I want to participate in this research and continue with the survey. Yes No